

ExAMPLER Executive Summary Roadmap

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1 Introduction

This roadmap document is concerned with how agent-based social simulation can make use of the next level of exascale high performance computing and not get left behind as new technology is introduced. Exascale is the next level beyond the existing petascale level of high performance computing. Exascale is defined as 1×10^{18} double precision floating point operations per second and its speed is dependent on parallel accelerators, for example Graphics Processing Units (GPUs), which have many thousands of processing cores. A review of agent-based social science publications has shown that high performance computing is an under-used resource in this field, with the majority of models built to run on the users' laptops or desktops. This puts the social simulation community at a disadvantage when the current UK roadmap for academic high performance computing is moving towards exascale computing. At the present time, social simulation is under-represented in high performance computing, which has traditionally been the domain of areas like physics, astrophysics, quantum computing, climate, weather and electronics. A roadmap is needed to show how agent-based social simulation can step up to the next scale of computing as there is reason to believe that the models being built are not suitable for the accelerated computing infrastructure.

2 Objective

The aim of the roadmap document is to provide a path into high performance computing for agent-based modelling and social simulation (ABMSS). If this can be achieved in the next few years, then the ABMSS community has the greatest opportunity to step up to the next level of computing as exascale is introduced. To begin with, a use case for why exascale is important to ABMSS is developed, along with the science case for why modelling at scale is important. Then, a roadmap towards achieving this change is constructed from a review of the technology. The reason for writing the roadmap is to demonstrate a case for exascale ABMSS and outline a path towards its adoption.

3 Methodology

To begin with, a systematic literature review (SLR) was conducted to identify prior use of high performance computing and agent-based modelling. This is intended to identify the computer languages or ABM frameworks used and the operating systems and hardware. A key question is whether ABMs are being written as bespoke programs, or whether ABM frameworks like NetLogo, MASON or Repast HPC are being used? In addition to the SLR, we have also organised a two day ‘visioning’ workshop in London and another two day ‘roadmap’ workshop in Glasgow. Shorter versions of the workshops have also been run at three ABM conferences in order to engage with active ABM researchers. The roadmap document is a community report drawing on the knowledge and expertise of multiple researchers in the fields who are included as authors.

4 Findings

The literature review has identified only 18 papers where high performance computing is used for large-scale agent-based models from a total of 3417. The anecdotal views of the researchers reading the papers is that most ABM papers are describing the science and not the computing required to achieve the results. This is borne out in the HPC part of the review where data on the scientific computing setup used is hard to find. In general, the 3417 papers read during the course of the review showed a lack of HPC use, with the majority of models running at the laptop or desktop level.

Figure 1 shows the frequency distribution of the number of agents for desktop PC based models (blue square) versus HPC models (red circle). This immediately shows the smaller number of HPC models, but the larger models are not exclusively HPC examples. The 10 million agent

column on the extreme right shows PC based modelling at this scale and no HPC. However, the raw number of agents is not the whole story as the agent’s computational complexity, the number of steps in the model, the number of runs and the size of the space they occupy are all contributing factors.

Figure 1: Distribution of the number of agents in models for PC (blue) and HPC (red). The x-axis shows number of agents from tens (10s) up to ten millions (10Ms). The y-axis shows the count of the number of models found at that level.

Looking at the number of runs for desktop PC and HPC models in figure 2, both PC and HPC peak at hundreds of runs (100s), with the highest number of runs for the biggest PC model only going into the hundreds of thousands (100Ks).

The model with the most agents is “Mitigation Measures for Pandemic Influenza in Italy: An Individual Based Model Considering Different Scenarios” in the journal PlosOne (2008) [Cio+08], which is an SEIR model with 57 million agents representing the total population of Italy. The largest number of steps in a model is 6,720,448,000, for “Exploiting Human Resource Requirements to Infer Human Movement Patterns for Use in Modelling Disease Transmission Systems: An Example from Eastern Province, Zambia” in PlosOne (2015) [Ald+15]. Here, the time steps are seconds for a model of human movement where there are 5000 agents and 4200 runs of the model performed for sensitivity analysis. This is labelled as a model using HPC as the authors state that the “Iridis 3 supercomputer at the University of Southampton was

Figure 2: Distribution of the number of simulation runs performed for the models for PC models (blue) and models using HPC (red). The x-axis shows number model runs from ones (1s) up to hundreds of thousands (100Ks). The y-axis shows the count of the number of models found at that level.

used to produce the migration paths for the agents in the ABM to follow”. It is stated that “Two separate computer programs were used to produce the observed results”, and it is unclear from the paper whether the ABM itself used the supercomputer. This shows how difficult it is to classify the hardware being used to implement agent-based models. The model with the highest number of simulation runs for sensitivity analysis (figure 2) is: “A food tax only minimally reduces the N surplus of Swiss agriculture” [Sch+21]. The 482,000 runs comes from the fact that the sensitivity analysis is the crucial part of the paper, which shows the effects of different policy changes on reducing the Nitrogen surplus of 3,300 farms in Switzerland. However, this figure is very difficult to obtain from the paper and requires interpreting a formula, along with the number of policy factors being tested, from a diagram. None of these papers provide enough information for somebody else to replicate the model and only describe the scientific results. The most significant statistic is that only approximately 3% of the sample of 3417 papers contained information on either the number of agents, number of time steps, or number of simulation runs.

The other question of interest is whether bespoke code or ABM frameworks are being used, as this will inform the direction taken by the roadmap’s recommendations. Is it worth putting effort into accelerating

a particular framework, or is it more effective to target best programming practices for exascale where models are bespoke code? The literature review gives no conclusive answer in this case, as both methodologies are being followed to different degrees.

In order to answer the framework or bespoke code question, a keyword search was performed on the 228 papers selected in the first round of the SLR from the original list of 3417 papers. This is the set of papers that was identified as potentially an ABMSS paper by reading the title and abstract. The methodology for the keyword search was to use the “pdfgrep”¹ utility to scan the paper text in the pdfs for keywords. Fragments of text around the keyword match were used to manually determine whether the match context was correct, for example, is a model really using NetLogo, or do they say something like, “Repast, Netlogo and MASON are ABM frameworks”? The keywords are all searched as case insensitive.

Table 1 shows the keywords and the number of occurrences of the keyword in the set of papers. NetLogo is the most frequent, followed by Repast, MASON and, surprisingly, AnyLogic, MESA, the Julia agents library, GAMA and SWARM. This is good evidence of the use of ABM frameworks, with NetLogo appearing in 31% of the papers (71/228) identified as potentially ABM papers.

Keyword	Count (228)	Percentage ($\div 228$)
netlogo	71	31.1
repast	19	8.3
mason	8	3.5
anylogic	7	3.1
mesa	3	1.3
agents.jl	2	0.9
gama	2	0.9
swarm	1	0.4

Table 1: Keyword search for ABM frameworks in the SLR papers. Keywords are case insensitive. NOTE: FlameGPU, ChiSim, PDES-MAS, Simudyne and SpatialOS all scored zero.

For the computer languages used, table 2 shows the keyword search for some popular ABM programming languages. However, this cannot be taken as bespoke development, as Repast uses Java and “PyNetLogo” links python and NetLogo, so these groups overlap with the frameworks. The smaller numbers do suggest a bias towards models using frameworks. NetLogo’s count of 71 is a long way ahead of Java’s 31, which overlaps with Repast and its count of 19. Repast also has a Symphony and HPC variant, which is C++, so figures for bespoke model

¹pdfgrep: <https://pdfgrep.org/>

development are difficult to estimate.

Keyword	Count (228)	Percentage ($\div 228$)
java	31	13.5
python	26	11.4
C++	12	5.3
julia	2	0.9
cuda	1	0.4
fortran	0	0.0

Table 2: Keyword search for computer languages in the SLR papers.

In summary, the analysis of the SLR papers shows enough evidence of ABM modelling frameworks being used to justify efforts to bring some of these frameworks to exascale. Bespoke models certainly exist, although the work to run these at exascale is going to depend on the developers. Agent-based modelling on the GPU is rare, with keyword searches for “GPU” (4), “CUDA” (1), “OpenCL” (0) and “FlameGPU” (0) supporting this. The model size graphs in figures 1 and 2 are interesting as they show significant overlap between the sizes of models running on HPC clusters and at desktop level. One conclusion that can be drawn from this is that the number of agents and the number of runs alone do not determine the computational complexity of a model. The PC and HPC distributions clearly show that HPC is much less utilised, so we assume that most models are not big enough to justify the time, effort and cost of its use. The final point is that the biggest models we find in the literature in terms of the number of agents and the number of runs are NOT running on HPC. This is not what was expected and could suggest that many of the models being run have not got to the point where the size of the model is a part of the problem. The model science is the driving factor and not how the model is being computed. The literature review does not contain the models that were abandoned due to a lack of computing resources.

5 Recommendations

Very few agent-based models are run for the first time with millions of agents. This would suggest that initial development is done at the small scale and the models increase in size as they are proven to be both correct and useful. The requirement is for a clear development path that starts with desktop models, jumps to petascale HPC and then provides a well defined route into exascale for the few models that will benefit. How to identify the models that would benefit from exascale is dependent on how much of the code is parallelisable. This can be determined from running benchmarks on the model with increasing numbers of

processors to determine the percentage of parallelisation. Further research is needed in this area, as the method of representing space in the model might be the key to how to parallelise. During the Glasgow workshop, there was a discussion around “Applications with space” that suggested that network graph based models could identify parallel non-interacting agent groups from graph partitions. Exascale is extreme scale computing and it needs to be recognised that not all models are suitable for extreme level parallelism. NetLogo is possibly the most used ABM framework, and so would provide an easy route to getting a lot of models working in a short space of time. Unfortunately, this is not an easy option as scaling the framework is significant work. The options presented are to transliterate NetLogo code into another language and run using a different framework (e.g. ReLogo). There is precedent of this with NetLogo running on Repast HPC, but papers in this area of research are not up to date [Ozi+13]. This will also not get to exascale, as there needs to be an accelerator path from petascale HPC to exascale by making extensive use of GPU accelerators. One option that was suggested was to assume that sensitivity analysis, where models are run multiple times with different starting parameters, would be a form of parallelism. Unfortunately, the analysis shows that a model that is not doing “in run” acceleration cannot achieve exascale. Simply running the same, unaccelerated, model multiple times in parallel does not make use of acceleration and should be run at petascale instead. The recommendation for both the identification of models that could benefit from exascale and for bespoke model development is that “Proxy Apps” targeting ABMSS are an urgent requirement. A Proxy App is defined as a piece of code that simulates doing “useful” work in a self-contained way, where a benchmark is an artificial test of compute speed. A Proxy App for ABMSS might be an implementation of the “Daisy World” model [WL83], while a benchmark would simply time how long it takes to multiply a million double precision floating point numbers.

One final point about exascale computing and ABMSS came from our London workshop. Exascale is expensive due to the power requirements and getting compute time on such a scarce resource is also likely to be difficult. This led to a discussion about emulator models, where time on the exascale computer could be used to build an emulator model that produces the same results as the parent model, but only requires a fraction of the compute resources. The idea is to use the exascale computer to optimise a model that could then be run by multiple users at laptop or desktop level to test policy interventions. This would provide maximum payback on the initial exascale investment in computer time.

6 Conclusion

The systematic literature review shows that high performance computing is currently under-used in agent-based social science research with just 18 papers found out of 3417.

The number of agents in the model is not a good test of whether a model is big enough to require exascale computing. Model complexity needs to be a combination of number of agents, number of model steps, number of repetition runs (sensitivity analysis) and the geographic size of the model world. As yet, there is no “complexity index” that we can derive from the data to separate desktop models from HPC models. There also needs to be consideration for the computational complexity of the agent update step algorithm and the time required for communication between interacting agents. These factors require computing benchmarks for model speed, which were absent in almost all the papers.

The route from desktop to HPC can be achieved through a number of methods. Bespoke code has the option of recompilation on the higher performance target system. Where there is dependence on an ABM framework, either the framework needs to be ported, or the code modified to use a framework that is supported by HPC. The next step to exascale is harder and will require benchmarking to identify which models will benefit and which will not. The key is in the ability to make best use of the accelerator architecture, which can be established using a ‘step-up’ machine containing a suitable GPU card. This will either require bespoke code to be developed for the accelerator, for example using CUDA, or by using a GPU accelerated ABM framework like FlameGPU. However, this has yet to be tested at the level of exascale, which is where the development of Proxy Apps, that allow algorithmic improvements to be tested and benchmarked, are key.

One idea which comes from the requirement to port ABMs between frameworks is to have a definition of the model which is agnostic to the framework, programming language and hardware. Transliteration of code between programming languages is possible and programs like “ReLogo” to convert from NetLogo to Repast and on to HPC have been covered. This idea will require stricter standards on the definition of what a model is and how the instructions in the model operate, much like the C++23 standard is used for C++ compilers. This is currently lacking for the modified Logo language which underpins NetLogo.

In conclusion, the science case for exascale ABMSS can be made from the data obtained in the systematic literature review. Exascale is extreme level computing and not all agent based models are going to be suited to this architecture. The key is to begin to develop expertise in this area, which will then filter down and make the step up to exascale easier.

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